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An Assessment of the Relationship between Collective Memory and Place Identity

Kollektif Bellek ile Yer Kimliği Arasındaki İlişkinin Değerlendirilmesi

ABSTRACT

In the hustle and bustle of the day, the global world order has transformed into areas where people's lives are defined on the axis of living and working. Individuals and societies sustain their lives in an existential struggle in identity-free urban areas with a feeling far from the concept of belonging.

The concept of identity basically refers to a concept expressed through people. Place identity defines the perception of identity transmitted to places and living spaces through people. In this context, places and spaces gain identity through the materialization of the emotional accumulation of feelings of belonging, experiences, and memories. This concept is expressed as urban identity through cities and place identity through spaces. Place identity represents the place or accumulation where personal feelings are found in social experience. Therefore, what becomes important here is the concept of memory. Because the images, memories, and accumulations formed in our minds regarding living spaces are all intertwined with a past and form the movement of holding on to life for the future. Emotional ties are decisive at this point, and place identity forms the identity of the place that is fed by the memories and experiences created collectively by the individuals living there.

In this research, firstly the literature on the concepts of city and place identity is examined in detail and the concepts of collective memory and place attachment are evaluated on an environmental and spatial basis. The study is essentially presented as a reading and analysis study on the relationship between the concept of place identity and collective memory.

Keywords: Place identity, place attachment, collective memory

ÖZET

Küresel dünya düzeni, günün koşturmacası içinde insanların hayatlarının yaşam ve çalışma ekseninde tanımlandığı alanlara dönüşmüştür. Bireyler ve toplumlar, aidiyet kavramından uzak bir duyguyla, kimliksiz kentsel alanlarda, varoluşsal bir mücadele içinde yaşamlarını sürdürmektedirler.

Kimlik olgusu temelde insan üzerinden ifade edilen bir kavramı ifade etmektedir. Yer kimliği, insanlar aracılığıyla yerlere ve yaşam alanlarına iletilen kimlik algısını tanımlar. Bu bağlamda yerler ve mekanlar; aidiyet duygularının, deneyimlerin, anıların duygusal birikiminin somutlaşmasıyla kimlik kazanırlar. Bu kavram, kentler aracılığıyla kentsel kimlik, mekanlar aracılığıyla yer kimliği olarak ifade edilir. Yer kimliği, kişisel duyguların toplumsal deneyimde bulunduğu yeri ya da birikimi temsil eder. Dolayısıyla burada önemli hale gelen şey bellek kavramıdır. Çünkü yaşam alanlarına ilişkin zihnimizde oluşan imgeler, anılar ve birikimler, hepsi bir geçmişle iç içedir ve gelecek için hayata tutunma devinimini oluşturur. Duygusal bağlar nu noktada belirleyicidir ve yer kimliği; orada yaşayan bireyler tarafından kolektif olarak yaratılan hafıza ve deneyimlerden beslenen yerin kimliğini oluşturur.

Bu araştırma temelinde, öncelikle kent ve yer kimliği kavramlarına ilişkin literatür ayrıntılı olarak incelenerek, kolektif bellek ve yer bağlılığı kavramları çevresel ve mekansal bir temelde değerlendirilmektedir. Çalışma özünde yer kimliği kavramı ile kolektif bellek arasındaki ilişkiye dair bir okuma ve irdeleme çalışması olarak sunulmaktadır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Yer kimliği, yere bağlılık, kolektif bellek

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of identity is the concrete expression of an abstract situation that is multidimensional, discussed both conceptually and socially, and nourished by the combination of ways that a person experiences in life, which constitutes the self of a person, shaped by a deep past.

In terms of cities and architectural products, the phenomenon of identity and urban image includes a very broad definition that stands out primarily with its visual dimension and also includes natural, geographical, cultural products and social life norms. Urban identity and related urban images are formed over a long period of time and sometimes from very different components within the urban space (Ulu&Karakoç, 2004).

One of the important factors driving identity in 21st century cities is the concept of globalization. In the light of globalization and technological developments, it is possible to talk about a process of social change in which all kinds of values and information reach different parts of the world. Although commenting positively or negatively on the results of globalization on cities varies depending on the point of view, it is clear that it has mostly negative effects on the concept of identity. Because the concept of urban identity describes the unique social, cultural and architectural existence of cities, these concepts lose their qualities in the political discourse that has settled with globalization. Today, in many cities of the world, the clothing and nutrition industry and cultural values continue their existence in the shadow of globalization. Therefore, world cities are also heavily affected by this change.

In this context, it would not be wrong to say that today's cities have become uniform and their unique qualities have disappeared over time. In addition, the fast lifestyle based on consumption, seen especially in big cities and resulting from the globalizing world order, eliminates the concept of urban belonging, which expresses the enjoyment of the city and the emotional bonds established between people and their environment. Within the scope of the study, the concept of place identity and its sensory context are examined mainly on the basis of belonging and collective memory.

2. IDENTITY

Concept of identity; It was first used in France in the 1570s in response to the concept of "sameness". In sociology, it is considered as a concept that determines the social situation of the individual, and in psychology, it is considered as the whole of the features that distinguish the individual from other individuals (Yavuz&Zavalsız 2015). Identity is a complex issue. It essentially refers to a way of expressing or conceptualizing oneself and may incorporate personal roles and attributes, memberships in social groups or coteries, and connections to geographic location. It also includes internal definitions that include some real characteristic structure, some hopes, aspirations, and some feared possibilities (Devine-Wright & Clayton, 2010).

Identity is a multifaceted social concept, a sensory process, and also a clear expression of individuality. Identity is the set of relationships that constitute the individual's reason for existence, commitment and roots, representation and belonging. It is an interactive formation, an abstract concept that feeds on and nourishes the society in which it exists.

2.1. Place Identity

'Place' is the core concept of environmental psychology (Lewicka, 2008). 'Place' is the core concept of environmental psychology. The word 'Place' transitions between many different dimensions such as what is felt on a physical scale, what is symbolic, what is known and experienced versus what is unknown and unexperienced, and it also includes the effects of the meaning that users give to it through personal, social and cultural processes. While "Kant" claims that our knowledge of place is a prior knowledge obtained without learning, "Poincaré" states that it is related to our perception skills, and "Piaget" states that various definitions of place emerge through human behavior (Yalçın, 2012). Different concepts are used to name people's relationship with place; place attachment, place satisfaction, place identity, place dependence, sense of place, community attachment, sense of community. Each carries somewhat different meanings, and the exact difference between them is not clear (Kamalipour *et al.*, 2011). However, although there is a consensus on the definition of place and its differences from the concept of area, there is more disagreement on how people's ties to place (place attachment, place identity, spirit of place, place dependence, etc.) can be explained and measured (Lewicka, 2008).

Among this abundance of concepts used to explain people's relationship with place, two are based on the assumption of predicting people's behavior regarding the history of their places of residence, and these are place attachment and place identity (Lewicka, 2008):

- ✓ Place attachment: describes the bonds people form with places. The three components of place attachment are emotional, cognitive and behavioral components, with the affective component being the most frequently measured. For this purpose, numerous place attachment scales have been constructed. Environmental aesthetics research shows that people generally prefer historical places to modern architecture. Historic sites create a sense of continuity with the past, embody group traditions, and facilitate place attachment.
- ✓ Place identity: The word 'identity' describes two elements; uniformity and distinctiveness (uniqueness), and therefore the term place identity must encompass both aspects. However, if you pay attention, the concept of identity can carry two different meanings when adapted to place. In the first sense, the feature of 'identity' in the formation of the place; It ensures continuity and clarity over time. The concept of 'Genius Loci' is used to describe the intangible but unique character of the place and reflects the meaning of place identity.

While some 'place' theorists have suggested that identity is inherent in local physical form and materiality, recent theorists have expanded this definition to include the social formation of place. Some theorists (Dolores Hayden and Doreen Massey) have argued that the identity of an area is a mixture of its physical condition and the social narratives associated with it. Massey (1994), In his work 'Global sense of place', he argued that place is the interweaving of social relations, meetings, and gatherings for a particular group in a particular place. In this context, the physical aspects of a region are important as a location that enables social narratives to match (Larco, 2010).

The concept of place identity has a long history, dating back to Prohansky's work in the 1970s and 1980s and Altman and Low's (1992) seminal publications on place attachment (Devine-Wright&Clayton, 2010). Low establishes six types of relationships between humans and the environment. These are the hereditary relationship, the relationship arising from losing one's homeland, the economic relationship, the cosmological relationship, the relationship based on holiness, the relationship based on narratives.

In people's experiences of place, physical form, activities, and cultural meanings combine to create a sense of place (Montgomery, 1998). Meaning and engagement affect imageability and are influenced by culture and experience. It also affects people's identity and supports the continuity of life and socio-cultural values. Due to the changing contexts of urban centers affected by globalizing culture and built forms, it is imperative to examine the psychological dimensions (attachment and perception) in the placemaking process. Because of its importance in developing and protecting individual and group identities, place attachment can be used as a structural element in the identification of a place (Ujang, 2009).

Prohansky et al. (1983) defined place identity as a mixture of memories, concepts, interpretations, ideas, and types of settlements that include emotions associated with distinct physical locations. As a distinctive infrastructure, place identity can function to solidify personal identities, define actions or activities, tastes and preferences, and mediate efforts to change the environment (Dixon and Durrheim, 2000).

Studies conducted by Kaplan (1983) and Korpela (1989) examine the environmental component of identity as an effective product of self-control. In this case, the environment must be taken into account not only as a mediator in the regulation of social relations, but also with what it represents in or within itself. It appears that the environment is used by the individual to maintain his or her positive self-esteem by preserving his or her identity (Fleury-Bahi *et al.*, 2008).

The relationship between place, identity, and experience is a controversial aspect of social theory. With postmodern theory, place is not defined as a static, possible or objective phenomenon, but is expressed as a continuous and dynamically structured phenomenon. The experiential and cultural importance of places and the function of the environment in identity formation are examined within the framework of various disciplines. This type of work focuses on the sense of belonging, attachment to place, the contrast between 'home and 'outside' and the creation of problematics, center and periphery, or place and non-place areas. (McCabe&Stokoe, 2004).

Place identity is typically applied to urban concepts, but it takes on a new dimension when examined to understand its implications for the natural environment. Although awareness is increasing that the issue of identity is related to environmental problems, researchers are changing the direction of the discussion by

creating some conceptual confusion with terms such as the sources of identity, the nature of identity and the effects of identity. (Devine-Wright & Clayton, 2010).

Identity cannot be expressed simply, nor can it be considered separately from the quality of place, and it is neither a fixed concept nor one that changes and differs frequently. Identity can be thought of as the glue that holds people together and ties them to place, and is the opposite of rootlessness. It creates a sense of belonging and is a driving force that demonstrates sufficient strength to overcome some aspects of economic deprivation and physical decline (Aly, 2011).

2.2. Collective Memory

Although the subject of memory is mainly studied and researched in the field of psychology, it has an interdisciplinary feature because it is a human concept. Various definitions, different approaches, research and discussions on memory continue in many fields such as psychology, philosophy, sociology, social psychology, history, political science and educational sciences (Doğu&Deligöz, 2017). According to Sigmund Freud (1856-1939), whose interpretations of memory are still valid today, the practices of remembering and forgetting, which are directly related to memory, are the result of individual choices. Forgetting occurs when the subconscious suppresses the things that are not wanted to be remembered. This is also a way for the 'ego' to defend itself, and therefore to protect oneself. Throughout this process, Freud interpreted memory as 'individual'. In the same period, Henri Bergson (1851-1941) interpreted memory through images formed in the mind after perception to represent reality (Çalak, 2012).

Many theorists working on memory argue that the memory of an individual who is not in a social context that is separated or disconnected from all human relations will not be formed. Just as public memory is the sum of individuals' memories, individual memory is also a part of public memory and is shaped together with public memory. Even if buildings and roads change or are demolished, some spatial traces, such as the name of a square, a street or a store, remain in memory for a long time, because space regulates not only the movements but also the thoughts of a human group with its habits regarding the place. (Arslan&Uludağ, 2020). In other words, no matter how individually "memory" is carried, it only becomes memory within a social relationship network and in the process of socialization (Avcıoğlu&Akın, 2016).

According to Halbwachs, when viewed in a collective sense, memory is not a given but a socially constructed notion" In this context, memory has an aspect that characterizes being affiliated with a community. A person's relationship with a group, a community, outside of his or her own existence, and the perspective that this relationship reveals, is a form of memory and remembrance formed by a system of common values (Doğu&Deligöz, 2017).

Social/common representations, which are the most important elements that make collective remembrances possible, are symbols that shape collective memory and bring and nourish the sense of "partnership" and "belonging" that form the basis of collective memory. Collective memory, which is associated with a "place" that preserves its common identity, has historical continuity, and has meaning for those living in it, is embodied by being associated with the place(s) through these symbols that refer to the common past. Memories, events, people, etc. accumulated in the collective memory constitute some reference points in the space, and common spaces that give scale to the space and bear the traces of the values adopted by the society strengthen the memorability of the collective memory (Avcıoğlu&Akın, 2016).

2.3. Evaluation On The Relationship Between Collective Memory And Place Identity

What is important for a place to gain an identity is its unique characteristics and the connection people establish with that place. The memory spaces of the person or social pattern that is connected to that place for various reasons constitute the collective memory. Collective memory can carry people through good or bad times due to the emotional bond experienced with the place. What needs to be taken into consideration here is the positive development of the connection with the place through the correct organization of the physical environment. The spatial aesthetics of places will positively direct life experiences there.

The physical environments that constitute an important part of collective memory today have been deteriorating in many ways lately. This state of degradation, which starts especially in big cities, continues to include small settlements. The continuous construction brought by the age of urbanization has created a uniformity in the environmental texture. Therefore, places are about to lose their originality. Identity settlements with their own unique texture build a bridge between the past and the future as they have a greater place in the memory of the individual and society. In this sense, it is very difficult to find common ground socially and develop a collective memory in urban settlements where individualism is intense. It is

not possible to establish a bond of belonging with a place in this system that confines people to limited living spaces and asks them to always rush.

3. CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

Although the bond that people form with the place seems purely emotional, the basis of this emotional bond is a sense of belonging to the physical settlement. In this fast-paced age, it has become very difficult to maintain this sense of belonging. For this reason, human beings need to slow down their pace of life as soon as possible and strengthen their ties with the life around them. Otherwise, a flow of unhappy, depressed people who cannot enjoy life in identityless, impersonal living spaces will continue. In this sense, the environmental steps that need to be taken to protect and strengthen the urban environment and preserve the aesthetic value should be assimilated.

It is important to ensure the spatial, historical, environmental sustainability of a place and to do this, some issues must be taken into account. The question here should be "what are the elements that need to be taken into consideration in protecting the place and maintaining an aesthetic value?" Because when a place is adopted, it will serve the collective memory better. For this reason, some of the steps that need to be taken to strengthen place identity and create a positive collective memory are stated below:

- ✓ Necessary steps should be taken to preserve the authenticity of physical environments. While taking these steps, practices such as Slow City Movement and Smart Urbanization should be taken into consideration as a road map.
- ✓ Environmental sustainability should be taken into consideration and green environments should be protected. It should make it easier for people to access green areas. The positive effects of green areas on human psychology should not be ignored.
- ✓ In urban and rural residential areas, construction practices that will damage place identity should be avoided. The applications should be organized in a way that does not disrupt the silhouette of the settlement.

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